

ISic1075

I.Sicily inscription 1075

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Camarina

Place of origin (modern)

Kamarina

Provenance

Serracarcara, in a house

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Camarina, private house

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140555

1. Ταυρώπη,
2. χρηστή,
3. ἔζησε ἔτη
4. ιε΄.
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492701

EDCS 39102230

PHI 140555

Bibliography

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- 1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 04.0032
- Pace, B. 1927. Camarina: topografia, storia, archeologia. Catania. At 163 no.15
- De Spuches, G. 1864. Illustrazione d'alcune epigrafi e d'altri oggetti archeologici. *Bullettino della Commissione di Antichità e belle arti in Sicilia.* 1: 12-17. At 13

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